

Study of SPB® LNG Fuel Tank

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Abstract. From the perspective of protecting the Earth's environment, regulations are being progressively strengthened on the emissions of nitrogen oxides (NOx) and sulfur oxides (SOx), which are air pollutants emitted from ships. As one of the countermeasures to these regulations, the use of liquefied natural gas (LNG) as marine fuel is increasing. SPB®¹⁾ LNG tank has already been constructed for many projects of LNG carriers and F-LNG as a cargo tank, and also the design of LNG fuel tank is proceeding using the same technology. But compared to the cargo tanks in LNG carriers, the fuel tanks need to consider the following differences. (1) SPB® tank has a high degree of freedom in its shape, allowing it to be shaped according to the structure inside the hull form. On the other hand, the arrangement of supports and the stiffness of double bottom are also related to the stress of tank, making proper arrangement crucial. In the case of container ships, some reinforcement may be required to install the fuel tank in double bottom. Therefore, the correlation between double bottom strength, support arrangement, and tank stress are examined. (2) In the fuel tanks, the number of load-unload cycles increases compared to LNG cargo tanks. During this process, the liquid level changes up and down, along with temperature changes, causing cyclic stress due to temperature differences. In addition to the stress caused by the internal liquid, ensuring fatigue strength against thermal stress is important. (3) The tank structure must prevent sloshing at any liquid level. Since the liquid level in the tank gradually changes during navigation, it is necessary to ensure that sloshing does not occur at any liquid level. Therefore, such as swash bulkhead inside the tank will be considered as necessary. (4) When a ship is navigating within a port, the holding of tank pressure may be required. If the tank structure made from plates and stiffeners is exposed to high internal pressure, it is considered that the stress of tank components will be increased. In this paper, we have examined the above issues and their solutions through a design study of the SPB® LNG fuel tank to be installed in the hold of a container ship.

1) "SPB" is a registered trademark of Japan Marine United Corporation, which is categorized as Self-supporting Prismatic Shape IMO type B tank, developed by IHI Corporation.

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1 Introduction

SPB® fuel tank is classified as Type-B tank among the tank types approved by the IMO IGF Code. The tank consists of the primary barrier, which is the tank body, and the thermal insulation and support. The tank is independent of the ship's hull, and a partial secondary barrier is provided according to the IMO IGF Code. Currently, there are three types of materials used for the tanks: aluminum alloy, stainless steel, and 9% nickel steel. SPB® tank system has the advantage of high flexibility in tank shape, allowing tank shapes to be made to match the hold space, and tanks with good volumetric efficiency can be installed. In addition, the swash bulkhead can be placed inside the tank, and loading and operation at any liquid level is possible without the problem of sloshing inside the tank [1][2]. In the case of fuel tanks, there are cases where pressure must be maintained inside the tank in anticipation of offshore waiting. SPB® tank may be capable of handling such high pressures. The design of the fuel tank can be partially based on the methodology used for the cargo tanks, but there are various issues specific to fuel tanks that require careful consideration. Therefore, in this paper, we carried out a study of the LNG fuel tank to be installed in the hold space of a large container ship and identified problems and considered countermeasures. The LNG fuel tank under consideration has a volume of 10,000m³, material of aluminum, and tank type: Type-B prismatic tank. Figure 1.1 shows the LNG fuel tank concept under consideration. For the

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calculation, the ship motion analysis in waves of a large container ship was carried out to obtain the acceleration generated in the tank, which was then used in this study.

Figure 1.1 LNG Fuel Tank Concept

2 Effect of Double Bottom Stiffness

The height of the double bottom in the hold of a normal container ship is about 2.0m, and it is required to have strength against the container load and external wave pressure. When the LNG fuel tank is installed in this hold, the stiffness of the double bottom affects the tank strength. When the space in forward and aft ward of the space in which the LNG fuel tank is installed is a container cargo hold, it is also necessary to ensure the continuity of the double bottom members, and it may be difficult to provide sufficient reinforcement. If sufficient reinforcement is not provided, the stiffness of the double bottom will be low, and the reaction forces will be concentrated on a part of the tank support, and the concentrated load will flow into the LNG fuel tank. Increasing the height of the double bottom can therefore be considered as one way of improving the stiffness of the double bottom. In this study, FEM structural analysis was performed for two cases: Case-1, where the LNG fuel tank is installed on the double bottom of normal height, and Case-2, where the LNG fuel tank is installed on the double bottom of increased height up to about twice of Case-1, and the problems in both cases were extracted and a realistic structural arrangement was investigated. Figure 2.1 shows the examples of LNG fuel tank installation in Case-1 and Case-2. The LNG fuel tank considered in this study has a restricted tank height and large tank width, so the structural arrangement is based on a longitudinal girder main structure. In addition, because the tank is long and wide, swash bulkheads are placed at the center line and in the middle of the tank in the fore-aft direction as a countermeasure against the sloshing. Note that in Case-2, the increase in double bottom height is limited to the compartment of the fuel tank. High stresses occur in the areas forward and aft ward of the fuel tank space due to the discontinuity of the double bottom structure, but it has been confirmed that the structure can be made viable by reinforcement through increased plate thickness and the application of high strength materials.

Figure 2.1 Example of LNG Fuel Tank Installation (Section)

The conditions for the FEM structural analysis performed in both cases are as follows:

Tank Dimension (LxBxD)	: 22m x 38m x 14m	
Cargo Density	: 0.5 ton/m ³	(LNG)
Vapor Pressure	: 0.7 barg	(in LNG Fuel Tank)

Tank Condition : Full Load
 Wave Condition : Which corresponds to (Maximum means Max. value in 25 years)
 Maximum Vertical Acceleration of LNG Fuel Tank (Az-max condition)
 (Ax, Ay, Az = 0.02G, 0.07G, 0.34G)
 Maximum Lateral Acceleration of LNG Fuel Tank (Ay-max condition)
 (Ax, Ay, Az = 0.01G, 0.22G, 0.03G)

2.1 Deformation of Double Bottom

The deformation of the double bottom was compared for Az-max condition, where the effect of double bottom stiffness is more pronounced. The load diagram of the whole ship FEM model for Az-max condition is shown in Figure 2.2, the deformation diagram of the whole ship FEM model is shown in Figure 2.3, the deformation diagram around the LNG fuel tank in Figure 2.4, and the displacement of the double bottom under the LNG fuel tank is shown in Figure 2.5. As shown in Figure 2.4, the double bottom deformation of Case-1 in the longitudinal center of the LNG fuel tank hold space is larger than that of Case-2. As shown in Figure 2.5, the maximum value of the displacement is approximately 9 mm in Case-1, while it is reduced to approximately 4 mm in Case-2, which clearly demonstrates the effect of improving stiffness by increasing the double bottom height.

Figure 2.6 Tank Bottom Support Arrangement (Plan)

Case-1: Normal Height Case

Case-2: Increased Height Case

Figure 2.7 Vertical Reaction Force of Tank Bottom Support [Unit: ton]

2.3 Tank Stress

Table 2.1 summarizes the maximum equivalent stress values of the primary members of the tank in Az-max condition. From these results, it was confirmed that the stress generated in the center line bulkhead and longitudinal girders placed above the tank supports is lower in Case-2 than in Case-1. This is because the double bottom deformation in Case-1 is larger than that in Case-2, resulting in a larger variation in the reaction force of the tank support, and the generated stress is higher at the points where the reaction force of the tank support is large.

Table 2.1 Equivalent Stress Comparison between Case-1 and Case-2 [Unit: N/mm²]

Tank Part	Case-1	Case-2	Diff.[%]
Bottom	29.4	29.4	100.0
Side Shell	33.3	33.3	100.0
Top	30.4	29.4	96.8
Hor. Girder	111.2	110.9	99.7
Long. Girder	108.8	104.8	96.4
C.L. BHD	59.8	53.9	90.2
End BHD	37.2	36.3	97.4
Swash BHD	101.9	97.0	95.2

In the two load cases of Az-max. and Ay-max. condition for which FEM structural analysis was performed in this study, the reinforcement is required for the primary members such as the horizontal girder and the longitudinal

girder. The required thickness of the primary members is shown in Table 2.2. For example, for the longitudinal girder, the web plate thickness in the original as initial scantling is 16 mm, but must be scantling up to 20mm, taking into account the availability of aluminum plate material and the efficiency of tank fabrication, in addition to the reinforcement based on the results of FEM structural analysis.

Table 2.2 Required Thickness [Unit: mm]

Tank Part	Initial Scant.	Required Thickness	Diff.[%]
Hor. Girder	16	20	125.0
Long. Girder	16	20	125.0
Swash BHD	12	16	133.3

2.4 Cost Evaluation

Based on the above results, the tank weight and cost were estimated. The tank weight of Case-1 was about 5% heavier than that of Case-2. On the other hand, the weight increase of the hull due to the increased height of double bottom around LNG fuel tank in Case-2 was about 1% of the hull weight. Furthermore, when the manufacturing costs of the tank and the hull were estimated and the total cost was compared, it was found that Case-1 of the double bottom of normal height was about 60% lower than the Case-2 of double bottom of increased height. In this study, it was confirmed that the increased height of double bottom compared to the double bottom of normal height can reduce the reinforcement weight of the tank due to the suppression of tank stresses and the reaction forces of the tank support. However, even if some reinforcement of the tank was required, Case-1 with a normal height double bottom was more cost effective. In actual design, the optimal structural arrangement considering cost performance is required.

3 Fatigue strength evaluation due to thermal stress

LNG fuel tanks are subject to more frequent fluctuations in liquid level and thermal stress fluctuations compared to LNG carriers. Therefore, fatigue strength against thermal stress fluctuations may become an issue. In this study, fatigue strength analysis of tank structural members due to thermal stress fluctuations was carried out, and its impact and countermeasures were considered. The calculation conditions were parametrically set with five cases of temperature difference between the tank top and tank bottom (60, 70, 80, 90, and 100°C), and the number of cycles was according to the IGF code. The calculation method was to calculate thermal stress using a coarse mesh tank model, and then calculate the fatigue damage of the butt welds of the tank structural members and the fillet welds of the primary members and stiffeners, taking into account the stress concentration factor due to fabrication tolerance.

3.1 Calculation of Fatigue Damage Factor

The cumulative fatigue damage factor C_w is calculated in accordance with the linear damage theory (Miner's theory), as shown below. In this study, only the calculated values of the loading-unloading components are indicated.

$$\sum \frac{n_i}{N_i} + \frac{n_{Loading}}{N_{Loading}} \leq C_w \quad (3.1)$$

Where:

- n_i : number of stress cycles at each stress level during the life of the tank;
- N_i : number of cycles to fracture for the respective stress level according to the Wohler (S-N) curve;
- $n_{Loading}$: number of loading and unloading cycles during the life of the tank not to be less than 1000.
Loading and unloading cycles include a complete pressure and thermal cycle;
- $N_{Loading}$: number of cycles to fracture for the fatigue loads due to loading and unloading; and
- C_w : maximum allowable cumulative fatigue damage ratio

3.2 Working Stress for Loading-unloading Cycle

The stress ranges in fatigue analysis for loading-unloading cycle are as follows:

$$S = (S_{max} - S_{min}) \text{ (for loading-unloading induced stress including thermal stress)} \quad (3.2)$$

Where:

- S : Stress range in the loading-unloading condition
- S_{max} : Maximum stress in the loading-unloading conditions with thermal stress.
- S_{min} : Minimum stress in the loading-unloading conditions with thermal stress.

3.3 Working Stress with Fabrication Tolerance

Stress level defined in paragraph 3.2 does not include the additional stress due to fabrication tolerance. But in general, actual welded joints have the misalignment or distortion during the fabrication stage. Considering that such tolerance causes the local stress concentration, stress concentration factors due to misalignment, distortion and weld bead configuration will be applied to the stress values derived in paragraph 3.2.

- K_m : Stress concentration factor due to misalignment
- K_d : Stress concentration factor due to distortion
- K_t : Stress concentration factor due to weld bead configuration

3.4 Results

Figure 3.1 shows a sample temperature distribution diagram with a temperature difference of 80°C between the tank top and bottom, and the liquid level is at the intermediate level. Figure 3.2 shows the fatigue damage factor ($CW_{loading-unloading}$) due to the thermal stress component for each temperature difference, with the vertical axis $CW_{loading-unloading}$ nondimensionalized based on the value at 60°C. It shows the point at the tank skin plate butt welds of the side shell where the value of $CW_{loading-unloading}$ is large. Figure 3.3 shows the color contour diagram of the fatigue damage factor at the skin plate of the side shell under a temperature difference of 80°C.

From these results, the fatigue strength becomes more severe as the temperature difference increases. From the point of view of fatigue strength, it is advantageous to keep the temperature difference small, but the operational workload of temperature control increases, so it is necessary to set an appropriate temperature difference that combines the two.

Figure 3.1 Temperature distribution diagram when the temperature difference between the tank top and tank bottom is 80°C and the liquid level is at the intermediate level / stress distribution

Figure 3.2 Trends in $CW_{\text{loading-unloading}}$ Due to Temperature Differences at Points with Large $CW_{\text{loading-unloading}}$ at the Tank Skin Plate Butt Welds

Figure 3.3 Color Contour Diagram of Fatigue Damage Factor of Side Shell under Temperature Difference of 80°C (see Figure 3.1)

These results indicate that the $CW_{\text{loading-unloading}}$ value becomes larger when the stiffeners are arranged in the vertical direction where a temperature gradient occurs. Also, in the working stress with fabrication tolerance described in paragraph 3.3, there is a tendency for the stress value to be slightly larger in butt welds than in fillet welds due to the effect of misalignment. For this reason, $CW_{\text{loading-unloading}}$ is greatest at the butt welds. The reason why $CW_{\text{loading-unloading}}$ tends to be larger near the center of the stiffener span is thought to be because the relative displacement at the center of the stiffener span when it expands and contracts due to thermal loads is larger.

From the above results, the effect of thermal stress on fatigue strength in the LNG fuel tank was confirmed. To ensure this fatigue strength, it may be necessary to take countermeasures such as suppressing temperature differences to a certain extent.

4 Sloshing

Fuel tanks must be designed so that sloshing does not occur regardless of the liquid level. In this study, a sloshing analysis was carried out to check the internal liquid movement and generated pressure by periodically moving the tank, at three liquid levels of 25%, 50%, and 75% of the tank height, to confirm whether sloshing occurs or not. The calculation was carried out using the MPS method[3].

4.1 Condition

The motion amplitude was calculated using values from the response calculations of a large container ship, and the ship motion period was calculated using T_θ and T_φ from the CSR formula[4] below. A graph of the natural periods T_{tk-X} and T_{tk-Y} of the liquid in the tank calculated using the NK formula[5] below and the ship motion

period is shown in Figure 4.1. This result shows that there is a low possibility that the ship motion and the liquid in the tank will be resonant.

CSR formula:

$$\text{Roll period: } T_{\theta} = \frac{2.3\pi k_r}{\sqrt{gGM}} = 36\text{s} \quad (4.1)$$

Where:

k_r : Roll radius of gyration, in m, in the considered loading condition.

GM : Metacentric height, in m, in the considered loading condition.

$$\text{Pitch period: } T_{\varphi} = \sqrt{\frac{2\pi\lambda_{\varphi}}{g}} = 16\text{s} \quad (4.2)$$

Where:

$$\lambda_{\varphi} = 0.6(1 + f_T)L_{CSR} = 400\text{m}$$

f_T : Ratio between draught at a loading condition and scantling draught, to be taken as:

$$f_T = \frac{T_{LC}}{T_{SC}} \text{ but is not to be taken less than 0.5.}$$

• NK Rule formula:

$$\text{Natural period of longitudinal oscillation: } T_{tk-X} = \frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{l_e} g \cdot \tanh\left(\frac{\pi}{l_e} h_{lc}\right)}} = 4.2\text{s}(25\%), 3.8\text{s}(50\%), 3.7\text{s}(75\%) \quad (4.3)$$

$$\text{Natural period of transverse oscillation: } T_{tk-Y} = \frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{b_e} g \cdot \tanh\left(\frac{\pi}{b_e} h_{lc}\right)}} = 3.6\text{s}(25\%), 4.0\text{s}(50\%), 4.1\text{s}(75\%) \quad (4.4)$$

Where:

l_e : Equivalent tank length (m) for calculating the natural period

b_e : Equivalent tank breadth (m) for calculating the natural period

$h_{lc} = 3.5\text{m}(25\%), 7.0\text{m}(50\%), 10.5\text{m}(75\%)$: Liquid height under consideration (m)

Figure 4.1 Natural periods of tank liquid and ship motion

The analysis conditions are shown in Table 4.1 to Table 4.3. As analysis results, the pressure time series of representative points in the tank shown in Figure 4.2 is output. For comparison, Case 1-A is shown as an example of a resonant analysis, and Case 1-B is shown as an example of an analysis when there is no bulkhead inside the tank. The motion amplitude for Case 1-A was determined with reference to the maximum angular velocities of Cases 1 to 3.

Table 4.1 Simulation Condition

	Direction	Liquid Level	Motion Period	Amplitude	
Case1	Roll	25%	36s	23deg.	
Case2	Roll	50%	36s	23deg.	
Case3	Roll	75%	36s	23deg.	
Case4	Pitch	25%	16s	7deg.	
Case5	Pitch	50%	16s	7deg.	
Case6	Pitch	75%	16s	7deg.	
Case1-A	Roll	25%	4s	4deg.	*natural period
Case1-B	Roll	25%	36s	23deg.	*without bulkhead (Figure 4.3)

Table 4.2 Motion Center

ΔL	-25 m	from Tank Center
ΔV	20 m	from Tank Btm

Table 4.3 Simulation Parameter

particle diameter	200 mm
simulation time step	0.002 s
output step	0.05 s

Figure 4.2 Evaluation Points (P1, P2, P3, P4)

Figure 4.3 Tank construction without bulkhead (Case1-B)

4.2 Results

The results of sloshing calculations are shown in Figure 4.4 to 4.11. Figures 4.12 to 4.14 show the internal liquid motion in Cases 1, 1-A, and 1-B. In the case of resonance range with the liquid in Case 1-A, as can be seen in Figure 4.13, relatively large internal liquid movement occurs, but the movement is suppressed by the horizontal girder, so the generated pressure is not large. In Case 1 and Case 1-B, it can be confirmed that large flow is caused by large roll motion. In Case 1-B, the internal liquid is not resonant, but the amount of moving liquid increases due to the absence of swash bulkhead, generating large pressure. However, even if a pressure of approximately 100 kPa occurs, under realistic structural arrangements and plate thicknesses, there is no need for reinforcement.

In Case 1 to Case 6, the generated pressure is basically equivalent to static pressure, and the internal liquid movement is gentle, but characteristic pressure changes are seen in Case 1 and Case 4. In Case 1, evaluation point P3, the pressure rises instantaneously by about 20 kPa with each movement cycle. This is thought to be caused by the liquid moving over the bottom girder, which is placed at a height close to the liquid level and in a direction that hinders the internal liquid movement, causing a localized sudden rise in the liquid level. No particular reinforcement is generated at this level of pressure. Figure 4.12 shows the internal liquid movement. In addition, a pressure change of 10 kPa is seen immediately after the start of movement in Case 4 at evaluation point P3. This pressure change occurs over a period of about 4 seconds, and is thought to be caused by the internal liquid moving at its natural period of 4 seconds due to the impact of the start of the movement. Compared to cargo tanks, fuel tanks need to prevent sloshing at any liquid level, but it was confirmed that the tank in this case did not slosh from a nearly full load state to a low liquid level state. Furthermore, the tank shape is wide. The large container ships tend to have large roll motions. In this study, it was confirmed that the generated pressure is sufficiently small compared to the allowable pressure even if swash bulkhead is not located on the centerline.

Figure 4.4 Pressure Time Series (Case1)

Figure 4.5 Pressure Time Series (Case2)

Figure 4.6 Pressure Time Series (Case3)

Figure 4.7 Pressure Time Series (Case4)

Figure 4.8 Pressure Time Series (Case5)

Figure 4.9 Pressure Time Series (Case6)

Figure 4.10 Pressure Time Series (Case 1-A)
(4second of Roll period case)

Figure 4.11 Pressure Time Series (Case 1-B)
(without bulkhead case)

Figure 4.12 Pressure contour of cross section at center of tank (Case 1)

Figure 4.13 Pressure contours of the cross section at the center of the tank (Case 1-A)

Figure 4.14 Pressure contours of the cross section at the center of the tank (Case 1-B)

5 High Pressure Tank

In the event of offshore waiting, tanks without liquefaction equipment may require pressure storage. Normally, the tank internal pressure required for Type-B LNG fuel tank is about 0.7 bar, but it is necessary to handle pressure several times higher than this. A design pressure exceeding 0.7 bar exceeds the pressure for a Type-B tank specified in the IGC/IGF code. We are studying the tank strength when high pressure is applied. From a cost perspective, depending on the size and each condition of the tank, our calculations under certain conditions showed a slight advantage in adopting a high pressure tank over a liquefaction equipment. When high pressure occurs inside a rectangular tank, large tensile stress occurs in the tank skin plates and stiffeners. According to the formula of the NK rules [6], the axial force influence coefficient is also taken into account in the calculation of members to which pressure is applied. However, according to the application rules [7] for independent prismatic tanks under NK rules, the coefficient of axial force effects is taken as 1.0. This means that the axial force is not taken into consideration for LNG tank in usually. Further evaluation is required to determine the extent to which axial force should be considered for tanks in a biaxial state, where they are pulled forward, backward, left, and right. Fatigue strength is also becoming stricter, and measures such as densely arranging trans frames are also required to keep the stress value at high pressure low.

6 Conclusion

Although the study was limited in scope, the following findings were obtained regarding the strength of LNG fuel tanks.

- Double bottom strength effect

It was confirmed that the LNG fuel tank reinforcement can be reduced by increasing the double bottom stiffness. The strength can be ensured by providing appropriate reinforcement to the tank when the hull has a double bottom of normal height. When the costs of both cases were calculated, it was more advantageous to partially reinforce the tank installed on a double bottom of normal height when comparing the total material and manufacturing costs. However, this result may change depending on the setting conditions for material and manufacturing costs.

- Thermal stress fatigue

Fatigue strength was examined by changing the temperature gradient of the tank in several cases. It was found that the level due to thermal stress effects on fatigue strength in the LNG fuel tanks targeted in this study is provided. To ensure this fatigue strength, it may be necessary to take measures such as suppressing temperature differences to a certain extent. Temperature differences are deeply related to actual tank operations. In future work, it is

necessary to consider the acceptable temperature difference in actual operations and to evaluate the extent to which the temperature difference can be controlled.

- Sloshing

It was confirmed that sloshing would not occur at any liquid level by providing appropriate swash bulkheads. We also performed calculations for the case where the swash bulkheads were eliminated. For the tank size used in this study, the natural period of the liquid in the tank tends to approach when the liquid level is low, but the web depth of the girder resulted in a significant reduction in the sloshing load. In any case, it was confirmed that it is possible to design a tank that does not cause sloshing.

- Consideration of high pressure

When the internal pressure increases, the tensile stress generated in the tank components increases, and strength that takes this effect into account is required. However, further verification is required to determine the extent to which the effects of axial force need to be considered

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